

PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES RESEARCH OF PLANT FIBER MODIFIED PHENOLIC FOAM COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Abstract: With the advent of the world's energy crisis, the technologies of energy saving and environmental protection from exterior wall have gradually become hot topics in building industry. Phenolic foam has excellent flame retardant and heat-insulating properties, which can be used as exterior wall material. However, its brittleness and low strength limit the application. In this paper, natural plant fibers are added in phenolic foam before curing process, and the effects of modified method for the fibers and fiber content on the performance of the foam composite are investigated. The result show that the mechanical properties of the modified foam composite is highest when the length of raw plant fibers is 10mm and the fiber content is 5wt %. The corresponding specific compression strength of the modified foam is 55.3% higher than that of raw phenolic foam. With the treatment of fiber in flame retardant , the mechanical properties of the foam composite are good and the specific compression strength is improved by 33.7% with consistent heat-insulating and fire-retardant properties.

Keywords: Phenolic foam, natural plant fiber, composite material, heat-insulating, fire-retardant

1. Introduction

With the rapid development of the construction industry and the improvement of people's quality of life, exterior building of thermal insulation materials have achieved rapid development. It includes inorganic insulation materials,^[1,2] for instance, rock wool, glass wool, and organic insulation materials,^[3] for example, polystyrene foam, polystyrene particles slurry and polyurethane foam. Phenolic foam possess excellent flame retardant properties, thermal stability, thermal insulation performance, and so on,^[4,5,6] which becomes the preferred insulation materials for the construction industry at home and abroad.

However, phenolic foam has several weakness such as brittle, easy to powder dregs and high relatively opening rate.^[7,8] These deficiencies hinder its development application, so the preparation of high-performance phenolic foam has become an important research topic. Many different methods have been developed to improve the property of phenolic foam. Generally, they can be divided into two categories: one is physical method,^[9,10] adding

glass fiber,^[11,12] rubber,^[13] aramid fiber^[14] and hemp. But the interface problems and spread evenly are the difficulties of this method. The other is chemical treatment^[15]. The mechanism of chemical modification is to introduce long and flexible molecular chains into the rigid backbone of phenolic resin to improve its toughness, which can react with hydroxymethyl, methyl and phenolic groups to obtain block or graft copolymers during the Polycondensation reaction,^[16] such as epoxy resin,^[17] polyurethane prepolymers,^[18] Cardanol^[19] and polyethylene glycol,^[20] etc.

shen et al^[21,22]. prepared chopped glass fiber, aramid fiber reinforced phenolic foam and its sandwich composites. He gets systematic research on Modified foam powder rate, compression and shear properties, as well as the performance of the system and interface.

Desail et al^[23]. add different mass ratio of chopped glass fibers and aramid fibers mixed in phenolic foam as reinforcement to fabricate flexible, flame retardant and low-cost phenolic foam.

Ula grass(*Carex meyeriana*)^[24] is one of the

Northeast specialites of China and has a unique of weatherization performance and natural antibacterial deodorant performance, which is known as the new green fiber.^[25] This paper focused on optimizing the preparation progress of the foam and added different handled Ula grass fibers to the foam system, thus, the purpose was to investigate its mechanical properties and thermal insulation flame retardant properties by different contents and treatments of Ula grass .

2. Experiments

2.1. Materials

Phenolic resin was supplied by Shandong Shengquan Chemical factory. Both Tween-80 as surfactant, n-pentane as blowing agent and KH550 as coupling agent were acquired from Xilong Chemical factory. Phosphoric and p-toluenesulfonic acid supplied by Beijing Yili Chemical factory were used as curing agents. Flame retardants was purchased from Beijing Zhongtonglu'an technology Co., Ltd.

2.2. Experimental Methods

2.2.1. The fibrosis treatment of Ula grass

The Ural grass was chopped to 200mm length in Cutting machine and then utilized distilled water to wash away the mud, sand and debris, 70°C for three hours in the oven. Then the handled Ural grass was cut into a width of less than 1mm filaments along their own lines. The Monofilament length were 5mm,

10mm, 15mm and 20mm, respectively. When flame retardant was applied to handle Ural grass, it needed at least 6~7h to immerse the fiber and then 70 °C for one hour in the oven.

2.2.2 Fabrication of fiber-reinforced phenolic foam

A foamable solution was prepared using a solution of resol (90 g), Tween-80 (1.8 g) and KH550(0.9g), stirred at room temperature for 1 min. Then, Ula grass mats of different lengths and different fiber content were impregnated into the foam able solution and subjected to stirring at 500 rpm for 5 min to evenly mix the fiber. The following step was to add n-pentane(7.2g), Phosphoric and p-toluenesulfonic acid(14.4g). The mixed solution was uniformly stirred and the foam slab was made in a homemade mould(Shown in Fig. 1) and then placed in the oven at 70 °C for 2h.

2.3. Performance Test

1)Mechanical testing. Compression testing, by means of a universal testing machine (UTM5000, Shenzhen SUNS), was carried out in accordance with China National Standard GB/T8813-2008. The dimensions was 60mm×60mm×30 mm then compressed between two stain less steel platens with a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min until the samples deformed by 20%. Compressive strength was determined from the maximum load (in a range of strain 10%).

Fig. 1. The homemade mold map

2) Thermal Conductivity. According to Fourier's law of heat conduction, thermal conductivity of reinforced foam composite was measured by steady-state method. It was calculated by the following equation:

$$\lambda = \frac{\phi \Delta d}{A \Delta(t_1 - t_2)} \quad (1)$$

Where λ was thermal conductivity, ϕ was the power

of the main heating plate on Steady-state, d was the thickness of the sample, A was the area of the main heating plate, t_1 was elevated temperature and t_2 was cryogenic temperature .

3) Flame test. Flammability was assessed through vertical burning method in accordance with GB/T 8333-2008 method was shown in Fig.3. The dimensions was 100mm×10 mm×10 mm.

Fig. 2. Test configuration and Mimic diagram

Fig. 3. Sample geometry of vertical burning method

3 Results and discussion

3.1. The influence of modification on the surface of Ula grass fiber

Surface microstructures of Ula grass is shown in Fig.4. As can be seen, surface of Ula grass fiber is rough, there exist many microns protuberant structures, which effectively increase the interface

contact area of the surface of the fiber with a resin matrix. Fig.5 is the microstructures of grass treated by flame retardants. As seen from SEM images, a thin film of flame retardant covers on the surface of fiber, nevertheless the convex structure is not completely covered. The role of flame retardants may reduce the trench of surface thus decrease interfacial contact area of fiber and the resin matrix.

Fig.4. SEM images of Surface microstructures

Fig. 5. SEM images of microstructures of Ula grass treated by flame retardants of Ula grass

3.2. Microscopic morphology and mechanical properties

3.2.1 Microscopic morphology of fiber-reinforced foam

Fig.6 is the microscopic morphology of Ula grass fiber-reinforced phenolic foam composite. It is observed that all foams exhibit closed-cell structures, and fiber distribution is not uniformly distributed over the region, which indicates fiber density distribution presents trapezoidal change. The cell size decreases compared to that of raw phenolic foam, however the abscess type and size becomes uneven, especially the abscess nearly Ula grass fiber surface. This is because the Ula grass fiber has higher surface energy, easy to become the bubble nucleation points, so that the fiber and its surrounded by plenty of bubbles. But the bubble pore structure of heterogeneous composite materials makes the

bigger bubble under compression load easier broken due to the stress concentration, the small bubble pore for deformation was not damage, which makes the phenolic foam not fully display its compressive strengths. inside certain deformation.

(a)phenolic foam; (b)Ulagrass (5wt.%, 10mm) fiber-reinforced foam; (c)Ula grassfiber

Fig. 6. SEM image ofmicroscopic morphology of fiber-reinforced foam

3.2.2. Effect of Ulagrass fiber length on the properties of foam compression

When using 5wt % fiber treated by flame retardant t on the surface modify foam composite material, the influence of fiber length on properties of phenolic foam is shown in fig.7. The specific compression strength of Ula grass fiber-reinforced phenolic foam increases with fiber length when the fiber length is under 10 mm and reaches the maximum value at 10mm. Compared to raw phenolic foam, the specific compression strength of fiber-reinforced foam increases by 33.7%. When the fiber length is greater than 10 mm, its special strength decreases with the increase of Ula grass fiber length. The possible reasons are that Ula grass fiber diameter is small and texture is soft, when increasing fiber length, the fibers are prone to tangle and agglomeration phenomenon, accompanied by reduced resin invasive. At the same time, the long fiber lowers proliferation ability not equal to moderate length of fiber,

dispersion is not good, easy to block the bubble pore. it makes the fiber concentrate in the region of bubble pore, leading to fiber distribution and gas can't discharge in time, which forms defects.

Fig. 7. Image of Ula grass fiber length on the properties of foam compression performance

3.2.3 Effect of the Ula grass fiber content on the compression performance

Fig.8 shows the effect of Ula grass fiber content to the compression performance of the reinforced foam. As is shown, the specific strength of the Ula grass fiber reinforced phenolic foam increases to the maximum when the content is 5wt %, and then decreases with the increasing of the content. Ula grass fiber distributes along the cell walls, which enhances the compression capacity of the walls and then guarantee the stress transfer. Meanwhile, during the foaming process, the fibers orientate along the direction of foaming. Therefore, when compression loads on the foam, a part of load is transferred to the fibers through the foam matrix, which may enhance the compression strength of the foam. While, it's not better that the fibers is too many, for the viscosity of the resin may increase too much to process and the fibers cannot distribute well, what's more, too many fibers may destroy the well-organized structure of the phenolic foam and ultimately decrease the compression strength.

Fig. 8. Effect of the Ula grass fiber content on the compression performance

3.2.4 inflaming retarding performance and heat conduction of Ula grass fiber reinforced phenolic foam

Heat preservation of Ula grass fiber reinforced phenolic foam with 10mm-length-fiber content of 5wt % was tested and analyzed, as is shown in Table 1. The Ula grass fiber can hardly affect the heat preservation of the phenolic foam (PMR/%). The interface between the Ula grass fiber and the phenolic matrix is strong, and the grass fiber is thin enough with excellent heat insulation, so that the heat diffusion along with the cell walls is retarded, which results in the decrease of the heat conduction of the modified foam. However, the fire retardant may weaken the interface, and ultimately weaken the effect of heat insulation.

Table1 Inflaming retarding performance and heat conduction

Foam	Phenolic foam	Ula grass fiber/PF
Density/kg m ⁻³	50.1	55.2
λ/W/(m•K)	0.060	0.064
PMR/%	94.44	93.18

3.3 Comprehensive evaluation of Ula grass fiber-reinforced phenolic foam

As shown in fig.9, the modified foam has the best mechanics performance when Ula grass fiber length is 10 mm, fiber content is 5wt % and the surface is not modified. Special strength increases by 55.3% compared with pure phenolic foam; Ula grass fiber reinforced the by the impregnation of the flame retardant on the surface of the optimum comprehensive performance of composite foam, phenolic foam increased by 33.7% than the compression strength, thermal insulation, flame retardant performance are slightly lower.

Fig. 9. Image of comprehensive evaluation of Ula grass fiber/PF foam

4 Conclusion

Micro-scale convex structures of Ula grass fiber surface increase the interface area of fiber and resin matrix, which can effectively improve the mechanical properties of phenolic foam. Ula grass fiber proves to be the first selection for fiber-reinforced phenolic foam material owing to its excellent thermal and mechanical properties as well as the cheap environmental fiber. Ula grass fiber treated by retardant meets the requirements of flame retardant

insulation requirements, therefore it has a good application prospect.

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